

RENEWABLE ENERGY TRANSITION IN NIGERIA: FIXING THE LACUNAE

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ABSTRACT

Energy transition is a globally trending impetus for fiscal radicalization among nations of the world. Being a new regime of value chain to enhance climate utility, fiscal wealth and cleaner climates, Nigeria is not left out in the quest. This paper examines Nigeria's policy instruments for clean energy transition. It also identifies issues in the Petroleum Industry Act among other energy laws and their effect on fiscal cleaner climate in Nigeria. The paper finally appraises degree of enforcement of international treaties, conventions for a virile cleaner energy in Nigeria. The paper suggests fiscally and clemently viable reforms.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Energy is the mainstay of fiscal sustenance of many nations around the world. People use energy in their daily activities to power their domestic and official obligations²⁴. Multinational, supranational and national entities use energy to power their businesses for profit making. Energy is a key infrastructural catalyst for investment pool to any economy. Foreign direct investments thrive on surplus availability of energy such as electricity, gas, petroleum and recycled/renewable energy-given products²⁵. Energy infrastructure is a fulcrum to enhance economic development and wealth spread.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria is the largest oil and gas clime having crude oil which accounts for 90 per cent of its total export earnings and government fiscal or budgetary financing together with annual profit projections mostly relying on crude oil²⁶. However, Nigeria is being influenced and pressurized by the dynamics of global energy politics and policies, not limited to the Paris Agreement on Climate Change and universal commitments to transition to low-carbon energy, the oil and gas industry future now faces uncertainties²⁷. Global push from clean energy transition actors now creates bleak future for Nigeria's decades-long dependence on black gold, making it vulnerable to accessing support from international finance institutions which have continued to play the global politics of funding clean-energy related projects²⁸.

Nigeria stands to benefit from the global transition to embrace renewable sources of energy in three major critical ways: renewable energy as a source of foreign exchange earner, as a viable alternative source of energy for powering domestic utilitarian value chains and social investments priorities and as a panacea to the eschatological menace of carbon emission²⁹. Given the fluctuation in the price of global oil and gas, Nigeria now faces the consequences of her age-long failure to diversify to alternative

²⁴ See Online Article by Jack Dawson, The Different Uses of Energy in our Daily lives, available at <https://www.renewableenergyworld.com/energy-efficiency/the-different-uses-of-energy-in-our-daily-lives/#gref> accessed on 10 December 2023

²⁵ MDPI Publication, Foreign Direct Investment in the Power and Energy Sector, Energy Consumption, and Economic Growth: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan, available at <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/11/1/192> accessed on 10 December 2023

²⁶ See International Trade Administration Official Website: 'Report on Nigeria Oil and Gas Overview' <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/nigeria-market-overview> accessed on 8 Decemeber 2023

²⁷ See NIGERIA BUR 2 - Second Biennial Update Report (BUR2).pdf available at <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/NIGERIA%20BUR%202%20%20Second%20Biennial%20Update%20Report%20%28BUR2%29.pdf>

²⁸ NIGERIA BUR, ibid

²⁹ See pg8 of Ikenga Journal of African Studies Climate change as an act of "God" or "Man": An eschatological account Vol. 23, No.2, June 2022, available at https://www.ikengajournal.com.ng/admin/img/paper/23_2-9.pdf accessed on 11 December 2023

sources of energy, it therefore seems the country has again positioned itself as a spectator rather than a major actor in the energy transition mandate.³⁰ It follows that most of African economies are still underdeveloped considering energy deficit to fix critical infrastructures and stabilize their fiscal policies. Nigeria is in the bracket of developing economies with huge deficit in its energy provisions to fix critical areas of its economy³¹.

This paper examines the current policy instruments towards clean energy amidst just transition politics. The paper examines the defects in energy laws such as the Petroleum Industry Act among others on fiscal cleaner climate of energy transition. The paper finally appraises degree of enforcement of international treaties, conventions for a virile cleaner energy in Nigeria.

2.0 GLOBAL REGIME OF ENERGY TRANSITION

Previous energy shifts have unfolded over mankind's civilisation. According to the World Economic Forum, "a transition is not an abrupt change from one 'reality'³² to another, but rather a shift that unfolds generationally over considerable time, and one that may lead to greater diversity in the energy marketplace". More than 400,000 years ago, humanity began using biomass - primarily wood but also crop remnants and animal waste for fuel³³. Wood was an intuitive fuel; it was readily available, and the use of biomass as a source of energy would eventually retain its dominant role in the energy mix for thousands of years. The signal that a transition was imminent from biomass began when wood supply became scarce in Europe and price became unbearable.

Coal at that time was plentiful and, in many places across Europe, veins of coal could be seen on the earth's surface. The economics of coal also trumped its nuisance factor, so that despite the pollution it generated it became more and more economical to use coal instead of wood. In 1709, an ironmaster in Shropshire, England, Abraham Darby, discovered a process to turn coal into coke, which releases coal's sulphur as gas. Over the next 50 years, coke would come to replace charcoal from wood, in iron

³⁰ Nigeria has, since detection of oil been a mono cultural product nation mainly trading in fossil product as the main stay of its economic survival. The country is now in the dilemma between climate justice and net zero mandate.

³¹ African Development Bank on Nigerian Economic Outlook, available at <https://www.afdb.org/en/countries-west-africa-nigeria/nigeria-economic-outlook> accessed on 10 December 2023

³² See Govind Bhuttada February 13, 2023 Publication 'Visualizing the Past and Future of Energy Transitions' available at <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/sp/visualizing-the-past-and-future-of-energy-transitions/> accessed on 9 December 2023

³³ SaveonEnergy Publication 'Biomass Energy Overview' available at <https://www.saveonenergy.com/green-energy/biomass-energy/> accessed on 10 December 2023

smelting. Darby's invention marked the beginning of the coal era,³⁴ and the iron industry's adoption of coal in Europe became the first energy transition. Coal delivered, per kilogram, three times the energy of dry wood and throughout the 19th and 20th centuries it was the predominant energy source used in steam engines that powered the mills and factories of the great industrial revolution.

The second transition phase was the demand for oil and gas. In the nineteenth century, specifically 1859, oil was found in Pennsylvania, United States and its virtues were immediately clear³⁵. Kerosene, an oil distillate, became extremely popular in lighting lamps and providing illumination to many households. In the areas of energy density, adaptability, ease of transport and flexibility, humans were gradually turning to oil instead of coal³⁶. The industry that truly thrust oil into dominance over coal was the transport industry, with the manufacture of the modern-day car by Henry Ford in 1908. Car ownership, particularly in the United States became the main driving force behind oil. Along with the rising demand for oil, came increased supply in Russia, Saudi Arabi, Iran and of course Nigeria³⁷. Owing to the huge build-up of supply therefore, oil was cheap, and by 1964, oil finally took over coal as the world's number one source of energy³⁸.

Coupled with the oil transition is slow but systematically emerging fuel. The first shallow natural gas well was drilled in Fredonia, New York in 1821, but it took half a century before natural gas gained a significant foothold in the energy sources mix³⁹. The properties of natural gas initially made it a difficult fuel choice, even in Nigeria. Costly steel pipelines and trucks were required to transport gas from generation points to utilisation outlets⁴⁰. Without an effective way to reach markets therefore, gas was often wasted: allowed to burn/flare and vent into the atmosphere, especially when discovered alongside oil, which was usually the case then⁴¹.

The advent of liquefied natural gas (LNG) however brought gas to the global trade market. LNG allowed gas to be liquefied at extreme pressures and transported across the world in large quantities

³⁴ See Britannica's Abraham Darby British Iron Master, available at <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Abraham-Darby> accessed on 10 Decemeber 2023

³⁵ Wikipedia, Pennsylvania oil rush, available at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pennsylvania_oil_rush accessed on 9 December 2023

³⁶ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

³⁷ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

³⁸ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

³⁹ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

⁴⁰ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

⁴¹ Pennsylvania oil rush, ibid

through specially made vessels⁴². Once the vessel arrives its destination, the liquefied gas is re-gasified and then sent through pipelines to consumers. A truly global LNG market outside of Asia, in my opinion, took off only about two decades ago. This is the business model of Nigeria LNG, one of Nigeria's crown jewels and owned by the Federal government of Nigeria and other multinationals. With the discovery of gas and its many benefits which include: Its cleanness, its environmental friendliness, and its unique properties which make it the optimum fuel for cooking, commercial heating and power generation, gas, is gradually but surely emerging on the global platform as the primary transition fuel, in this current energy transition. Then, why another energy transition?

3.0 WHY THE CURRENT ENERGY TRANSITION?

The evolution of the energy industry as summarized had been driven by two primary propelling factors: industrialisation and economic advancement. The current 21st century transition is driven by environmental menace of carbon emission⁴³. The greenhouse gas cost to our environment, from the current energy sources primarily: coal, oil and gas cannot be ignored. Hence, the urgent ambition to reduce carbon dioxide (Co2) emissions, which is the primary source of greenhouse gases emitted through anthropogenic activities⁴⁴.

The simple definition of a greenhouse gas (GHG) is any gas in the atmosphere which absorbs heat and thereby makes the planet warmer than it otherwise would be.⁴⁵ The warmer the planet, the more vulnerable it is to catastrophic climate conditions, thus making greenhouse gases undesirable. The main GHGs in the atmosphere are water vapour, carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and ozone. Co₂ is however the primary greenhouse gas produced when fossil fuels are burnt. To tackle climate change and its negative impacts, a global emergency was declared and world leaders swung into action.

4.0 THE PARIS AGREEMENT AND FURTHER ACTION

⁴²See Enerdynamics on LNG History, available at <https://www.energyknowledgebase.com/topics/lng-history.asp#:~:text=Natural%20gas%20liquefaction%20was%20first,ground%20storage%20of%20natural%20gas> accessed on 10 Decemeber 2023

⁴³ Elsevier Climate Risk Management 39 (2023) 'Climate-driven risks to peace over the 21st century' available at <https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/283182/1-s2.0-S2212096322X00053/1-s2.0-S221209632200078X/main.pdf?X-Amz-Security-> accessed on 10 December 2023

⁴⁴ United States Environmental Protection Agency Publication, Overview of Greenhouse Gases, available at <https://www.epa.gov/ghgemissions/overview-greenhouse-gases> accessed on 10 December 2023

⁴⁵ See Britannica Definition of Greenhouse Gas Emission, available at <https://www.britannica.com/science/greenhouse-gas> accessed on 10 December 2023

The world leaders at the United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP21) in Paris, reached a breakthrough, called the historic Paris Agreement⁴⁶. The Agreement sets out long-term goals to guide all nations to:

- a. substantially reduce their global greenhouse gas emissions to limit the global temperature increase in this century to 2 degrees Celsius, while pursuing efforts to limit the increase to even a further 1.5 degrees Celsius⁴⁷.
- b. review their commitments every five years⁴⁸ and;
- c. provide financing to developing countries to mitigate climate change, strengthen resilience and enhance abilities to adapt to climate impacts⁴⁹.

In pursuit of this goal, the Agreement calls for a “balance” or what is referred to as “net-zero emissions” where greenhouse gas emissions produced, is the same as greenhouse gases taken out of the atmosphere. There have been various commitments by industries and countries in view of the Paris Agreement agreed to, by 192 countries in December 2015. Series of conferences were convoked by State Parties to implement the material content of the Paris Agreement until when the World leaders including Nigeria signed a climate pact in 2021 at the United Nations Climate Change Conference, COP26, in Glasgow, United Kingdom⁵⁰.

This underscores how very topical and critical the energy transition is. This is not unusual, because the impact of energy is far reaching, affecting every single human being. Energy goes hand in hand with economic activity. It lights, heats and cools our homes and places of work. Energy transports and connects people and goods through various modes of transportation. It is also used in agriculture and in the manufacture of steel, cement, plastics, medicines etc. This therefore answers the question that the current energy transition drive will be the single largest technological revolution known to mankind.

5.0 IMPERATIVES OF THE ENERGY TRANSITION FOR NIGERIA

Nigeria as a developing oil and gas exporting country is clearly at the crossroads with respect to the ongoing transition. Not only does it require increasing levels of energy due to its population increase, industrialisation and economic goals, it also generates over 90% of its external foreign exchange

⁴⁶ The Paris Agreement seeks to accelerate and intensify the actions and investment needed for a sustainable low carbon future

⁴⁷ Article 2 of the Paris Agreement

⁴⁸ Article 4 of the Paris Agreement

⁴⁹ Articles 6, 9, 10 and 11 of the Paris Agreement

⁵⁰ “The approved texts are a compromise,” said UN Secretary-General AntónioGuterres. “They reflect the interests, the conditions, the contradictions and the state of political will in the world today. They take important steps, but unfortunately the collective political will was not enough to overcome some deep contradictions.”

earnings from the sale of oil and gas resources. The planned, gradual, global transitioning, away from oil and gas is therefore cause for quick strategic thinking and collective action. At the COP26, the former President, MuhammaduBuhari committed Nigeria to delivering net zero emissions by 2060⁵¹. This was not without pointing the attention of developed nations to the following cardinal points:

- a. industrialised and advanced economies had access to stable and abundant supply of relatively cheap energy: coal, oil and gas. They are therefore responsible for the current climate crises as underdeveloped countries like Nigeria have contributed very little to historical GHG emissions. As a result, limiting our use of the same energy sources, utilised by these industrialised countries, without viable, inexpensive options, implied a curtailment of our own industrialisation.
- b. monetary commitments pledged to support developing countries in transitioning, based on the Paris Agreement of 2015, were still unfulfilled and needed to be made good.
- c. Nigeria, as a country with natural fossil fuel resources, cannot afford for international and multilateral agencies to stop funding the development of fossil fuels, particularly gas projects. Based on the above, Nigeria's approach to the ongoing energy transition presents opportunities that can be strategically delivered.

Therefore, a simple dual-fold approach should be: (a) to maximise value from existing oil and gas resources whilst paying close attention to the industrial development of our country; (b) intentional growth of the off-grid power and renewables industry taking advantage of foreign financial support and technology transfer.

6.0 POLICY AND REGULATORY INSTRUMENTS FOR CLEANER ENERGY IN NIGERIA

The regulatory instrument reflects the legal and structural framework of the Nigerian government on the implementation of renewable energy. Administrative bureaucracies and inefficiencies hinder swift progress, but there is a slow and steady advancement given the noticeable increase in the use of solar-powered energy sources in homes, institutions and offices in Nigeria. The following key documents and projects reflect the Nigeria's policy instrument and implementation of renewable energy transition. They are:

a. National Electric Power Implementation Policy 2001

⁵¹ See State House Press Release, At COP26, President Buhari Pledges Net Zero Emissions by 2060, Says Nigeria will Maintain Gas-Based Energy Transition <https://statehouse.gov.ng/news/at-cop26-president-buhari-pledges-net-zero-emissions-by-2060-says-nigeria-will-maintain-gas-based-energy-transition/#:~:text=The%20Statehouse%2C%20Abuja,At%20COP26%2C%20President%20Buhari%20Pledges%20Net%20Zero%20Emissions%20by%202060,Maintain%20Gas%2DBased%20Energy%20Transition&text=President%20Muhammadu%20Buhari%20Tuesday%20in,to%20net%20zero%20by%202060> accessed on 10 December 2023

In 2000, the federal government set up the Electric Power Implementation Committee to advise on reform of the electric power sector and the committee's efforts yielded the National Electric Power Implementation Policy 2001 (NEPIP). The NEPIP stipulates the general framework for Nigeria's agenda on sustainable power distribution with a particular focus on efficient distribution and utilisation.

b. National Energy Policy 2003

The National Energy Policy 2003 (NEP 2003) was recommended by the Electric Power Implementation Committee in 2003 to develop Nigeria's energy resources. The NEP 2003 places emphasis on the effective use of sustainable energy resources with a particular focus on solar energy and advocates for the aggressive integration of solar energy in the nation's power supply. It was later reviewed and replaced by the National Energy Policy 2013, which re-emphasised the importance of enforcement and implementation of sustainable energy goals while decrying the failure of implementation, energy loss, inefficiency and waste in the realisation of such goals

c. Renewable Energy Master Plan 2005

The Renewable Energy Master Plan 2005 (REMP) recommends the utilisation of renewable energy and seeks to provide an implementation strategy. It conceptualises Nigeria's renewable energy goals and tries to address the key factors for its attainment. The REMP projects that the minimum electricity demand in Nigeria shall be above 315MW by 2030. The goal is that over 20 per cent of the energy supply will be from renewable sources.

d. Renewable Energy Policy Guidelines 2006;

The Renewable Energy Policy Guidelines 2006 (REPG) is a document by the Federal Ministry of Power that details policy objectives for the development and utilisation of renewable energy. The REPG is very similar to the REMP, the major distinction being that the REPG places more premium on renewable energy generation and distribution. It also maps out a strategy for a cost-effective administration of the Renewable Electricity Trust Fund. In addition, the REPG provides incentives for the utilisation of renewable energy and recommends a five-year tax holiday as an incentive for investors in renewable energy in the hopes of encouraging the participation of more stakeholders.⁵²

e. Captive Energy Generation Regulations 2008

⁵² The NREEEP provides incentives centred around renewable energy, some of which include: (1) customs duty exemptions for two years on the importation of equipment and materials used in renewable energy projects; (2) five-year tax holidays for manufacturers from date of commencement of manufacturing; (3) five-year tax

The Captive Energy Generation Regulations 2008 (CEGR) were issued by the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) in 2008 to regulate captive generation of electricity for small or private use. It houses principles akin to those in the general regulations but applies especially to small generators or captors. The CEGR defines captive power generation as 'generation of electricity exceeding 1 MW for the purpose of consumption by the generator, and which is consumed by the generator itself, and not sold to a third-party'.⁵³ The CEGR also sets provisions for the licensing and regulation of captive energy generators.

f. National Renewable Energy Efficiency Policy 2013

The National Renewable Energy Efficiency Policy 2013 was conceived by the Federal Ministry of Power as a policy to foster sustainable power generation and consolidate the stipulations of the existing energy laws. It seeks to improve energy efficiency as well as to overcome the administrative and social barriers hindering the sustainable use of energy.

g. National Energy Efficiency Action Plans 2015–2030

The National Energy Efficiency Action Plans 2015–2030 (NEEAP) were adopted by the Inter-Ministerial Committee on Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency and approved by the National Council on Power. Although the template was adopted from that initially designed by the ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Efficiency, the NEEAP provides a strategic outlook on the situation in Nigeria with plans for the implementation of renewable energy goals. Specific focus is placed on effective energy, emission reduction, efficient lighting, monitoring, distribution and enforcements, and verification of standards of materials, homes, buildings and industries. The NEEAP also emphasises capacity building and the utilisation of local materials and workers. The inputs of the implementation of the NEEAP are to be monitored by the Federal Ministry of Power. The NEEAP also outlines the establishment of a system for monitoring, verifying and enforcing minimum energy performance standards⁵⁴

h. Order on the Mandatory Dispatch of Hydropower Plants 2019

This order was issued by the National Electricity Regulatory Commission in 2019,⁵⁵ requiring the off-take of power generated by the three hydropower generating stations in Nigeria before off-take from gas

⁵³ A core objective of the Electricity Act, 2023 (the “Act”) is to provide a holistic integrated policy plan that recognizes all sources for the generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity.

⁵⁴ The Plan covers significant energy efficiency improvement measures, and expected and/or achieved energy savings

⁵⁵ Order No. NERC/NERC/182/2019

-powered plants.⁵⁶

i. Energy for All – Mass Rural Electrification Programme 2020

This programme expresses the federal government's intention to power 304 healthcare facilities and schools across the country using renewable energy (primarily solar). This programme was introduced in August 2020 and will be implemented by the Rural Electrification Agency (REA) in collaboration with the existing agencies. In the bid to implement the Programme and its other pet programmes, REA in collaboration with the Africa Clean Energy Technical Assistance Facility (ACE-TAF) and the Nigeria Governors' Forum (NGF) organised a two-day sensitization workshop in May 2022 geared towards a better understanding REA operations and initiatives, to achieve implementation sustainability and enhance performance of its programmes (including the Energy for All- Mass Rural Electrification Programme).

j. National Climate Change Policy 2021–2030

The National Climate Change Policy 2021–2030 is aimed at implementing the mitigation procedures already put in place to promote a low-carbon, high-growth economic development plan for a sustainable environment in Nigeria.

7.0 LEGAL INSTRUMENTS FOR CLEANER ENERGY IN NIGERIA

Nigeria enacted the following statutory documents as framework for the operation of renewable energy in Nigeria, and are further determined by the policy and enforcement outlook:

i. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria

The former President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, MuhammaduBuhari on the 17th March 2023, signed into law the 5th Amendment to the 1999 Constitution⁵⁷ allowing states in the country to license generate, transmit and distribute electricity. This amendment presents a significant opportunity for foreign investors to enter the country's energy sector. This policy change provides foreign investors with new avenues to invest in the Nigerian electricity industry and tap into a market with immense potential for growth and development. Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa and has a population of over 220 million people.

The damming of water sources within Nigeria for hydropower generation and the establishment of renewable energy power plants in Nigeria by the recent fifth alteration to the Constitution are now under

⁵⁶ See Section 32 of the Electric Power Sector Reform Act

⁵⁷ Fifth Alteration (No.33) Devolution of Powers (National Grid System) Bill (the “Constitutional Amendments”).

both federal and state jurisdiction.⁵⁸ However, the Houses of Assembly of the states can now make laws for the generation, transmission and distribution of electricity that extend to areas within their states whether or not covered by the national grid system or to regulate power stations established by the states in this regard.

Electricity generation, transmission, and distribution were listed in the Concurrent Legislative List of the Constitution, which is a list that is defined under the Constitution as the list of matters which the National Assembly and a (State) House of Assembly may make laws to the extent prescribed in the Concurrent Legislative List. Specifically, paragraphs 13 and 14 of the Concurrent Legislative List (Part II of the Second Schedule to the Constitution) provide as follows:

“13. The National Assembly may make laws for the Federation or any part thereof with respect to-

- a. Electricity and the establishment of electric power stations;
- b. The generation and transmission of electricity in or any part of the Federation and from one state to another state;
- c. The regulation of the right of any person or authority to dam up or otherwise interfere with the flow of water from sources in any part of the Federation and from one state to another state;
- d. The regulation of the right of any person or authority to dam up or otherwise interfere with the flow of water from sources in any part of the Federation;
- e. The participation of the Federation in any arrangement with another country for the generation, transmission and distribution of electricity for any area partly within and partly outside the Federation;
- f. The promotion and establishment of a national grid system; and
- g. The regulation of the right of any person or authority to use, work or operate any plant, apparatus, equipment, or work designed for the supply or use of electrical energy.

⁵⁸ The Nigerian Constitution always allowed component **States** in the country the authority to generate, transmit and distribute electricity

“14. A House of Assembly may make laws for the State with respect to-

- a. electricity and the establishment in that state of electric power stations;
- b. the generation, transmission and distribution of electricity to areas not covered by a national grid system within that state; and
- c. the establishment within that state of any authority for the promotion and management of electric power stations established by the state.

The text which reads “areas not covered by a national grid system” in Paragraph 14 (b) of the Constitution had, for many years, been the subject of debate concerning whether states were prohibited from legislating on electricity matters (particularly generation) in areas covered by the national grid. On the one hand, an argument can be made that Paragraph 14 of the Concurrent List permits state governments to only generate, transmit and distribute electricity to areas not connected to the national grid (such as rural settlements lacking transmission infrastructure which facilitates the distribution of power from generation stations to end users). If the interpretative rule that the express mention of one thing in a statutory provision automatically excludes any other were to be adopted, this would mean that the Constitution intended for states to make laws permitting them to generate, transmit and distribute electricity if the laws are restricted to areas not covered by the national grid.

Another position, which also has some merit, is that states were not restricted from legislating on the establishment of electric power stations (i.e., electricity generation) given the text of Paragraph 14 (a) of the Concurrent Legislative List. The moral support for this position lies in the scarcity of power generation facilities which would, otherwise, satisfactorily cater to the needs of all residents in a state even where all areas of such state are allegedly covered by the national grid. With laws such as the Lagos State Electric Power Sector Reform Law, it would appear that the Lagos State government believes that the state’s requirements, influenced by its current population, makes it inclined to interpret the legislative intent in Paragraph 14 of the Concurrent List, as accommodative of legislating on state-powered electricity generation (and potentially, transmission, and distribution) to all areas within the states whether or not covered by the national grid.

Be that as it may, the foregoing discussions have now been put to rest by the Constitutional Amendments which altered paragraph 14 (b) of Part II of the Second Schedule of the Constitution reproduced above by deleting the word “areas”, and the text which reads: “not covered by a national grid system” both at paragraph 14 (b) of Part II of the Second Schedule to the Constitution.

8.0 THE ELECTRICITY ACT IN 2023

The new Electricity Act is materially symbiotic to the Climate Change Act as passed by the 9th National Assembly. The stratospheric negative ramifications attached to climate change have led to the critical drive for developing countries such as Nigeria, to curtail greenhouse gas (GHGs) emissions - by transitioning from the use of carbon-intensive fossil fuel energy to renewable energy options. The Electricity Act 2023 as signed into law by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu on the 9th of June 2023, proves capable of fostering renewable electricity in Nigeria. The Act is, therefore, evidently replete with imperatives for the development of renewable electricity which, when correctly implemented, could position Nigeria at the forefront of decarbonization and energy transition. The Act is weighted with provisions aimed at combating the negative effects of climate change by way of the utilization of renewable energy sources.

At the basal, it requires licensees to produce a specified approved percentage of their total power generation from a hybridized generation or from renewable energy sources, namely: solar energy, small hydro energy, wind energy, biomass. So, it can be affirmed that the Act is the harbinger for the achievement of low greenhouse gas emissions, the promotion of green growth and the encouragement of sustainable economic development.

The Electricity Act is structured such that the problem of electricity supply is adequately dealt with. Thus, the 2023 Act encourages embedded generation, hybridized generation, co-generation and the generation of electricity from renewable energy sources like solar energy, wind energy, tidal energy, hydro energy, hydrogen, and biomass, amongst a plethora of other renewable energy sources. It is now apparent why the provisions of the Electricity Act are almost entirely based on the promotion of renewable electricity, along with the implementation. Quite pithily, there are some specific features in the Act that support the development of renewable energy in Nigeria.

8.1 The Features of the Electricity Act 2023 in Support of Renewable Energy

The Electricity Act focuses on the development of renewable energy to the extent that the long title highlights its key feature of aiming to integrate renewable energy into the energy mix⁵⁹. In the first remove, the preliminary provisions set a target of creating an enabling environment for the optimal development of renewable energy. The Minister for Power's mandate to produce policy directives that detail measures for the development of the renewable energy sector is identified as favorable in this context.

⁵⁹ PMG Commentary on Electricity Act 2023, available at <https://kpmg.com/ng/en/home/insights/2023/06/commentaries-on-the-electricity-act--2023.html> accessed on 10 December 2023

Furthermore, the primary regulator of the electricity sector, the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), is empowered under the Act to continually promote the development of renewable electricity⁶⁰. There are also some financial measures adopted to facilitate the development of renewable energy such as a rural fund for renewable electricity projects, Feed-in-Tariffs, the N-HYPPADEC, and a renewable purchase obligation. These features are examined in seriatim.

8.2 Framework for Enabling Renewable Energy Environment for Investment

First, the Act vocalizes its overall intention to support the generation of electricity from a variety of renewable energy sources in various respects⁶¹. First, it aims to provide a framework for the development of renewable energy through the creation of an enabling environment for investment. Following, it is expected that the Act will interact with the barriers to the development of renewable energy. Relevant to renewable energy, is an objective to promote indigenous capacity in technology in the sector⁶².

This is timely in view of the identified problem of a deficit in the capacity to manufacture and maintain renewable energy technologies. As reiterated, the Nigerian masses are oblivious to the imperatives and benefits of renewable energy, partly accounting for its stunted development⁶³. The Act proposes to promote awareness and public education on renewable energy⁶⁴. Besides creating a clear context for addressing the barriers to the development of renewable energy, the obvious objectives will bolster investors' confidence to invest in the sector.

8.3 National Integrated Electric Policy and Strategy Implementation Plan (NIEPSIP)

Another identifiable feature of the Act is a policy that is aimed at driving the development of renewable energy. The Act authorizes the Federal Government through the Ministry of Power to adopt the National Integrated Electric Policy and Strategy Implementation Plan⁶⁵. It is apt to mention that policies have always been the precursor to birthing laws in Nigeria. The National Energy Policy 2003 birthed the Electric Power Sector Reform Act 2005, which was the primary law for the sector until the birth of the Electricity Act 2023⁶⁶. Thus, the National Integrated Electric Policy and Strategy Implementation Plan is

⁶⁰ The Electricity Act provides that the NERC, as the vertex regulator of the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (NESI)

⁶¹ The main regulation guiding renewable energy in Nigeria is the Electricity Act 2023

⁶² Generating energy that produces no greenhouse gas emissions from fossil fuels and reduces some types of air pollution

⁶³ According to Tracking SDG7's Energy Progress Report, about 92 million Nigerians – more than 40% of the country's population – lack access to grid electricity

⁶⁴ Section 185 of the Act

⁶⁵ Section 3 of the Act

⁶⁶ In 2005 the Electric Power Sector Reform (EPSR) Act was enacted and the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission

very significant in this context as it will continue to shape the evolution of law in the sector.

The Act defines the scope of the policy to include driving the optimal utilization of multiple sources to generate electricity. The sources include renewable energy sources such as solar, hydro, wind, biomass etc. It shall also contain measures for addressing the financial barriers to the development of the sector including waivers and subsidies. The Minister of Power is mandated to adopt the NIEPSIP within one year from the adoption of the Electricity Act 2023. They are also expected to review it every five years. While the Policy does not form part of the legal architecture given that it is not binding, it cannot be glossed over as it is emblematic and will continue to inform laws that promote the development of the renewable energy sector

8.4 The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC)

Under the Electric Power Sector Reform Act 2005, the NERC was vested with the overriding power to regulate the sector⁶⁷. The Electricity Act provides that the NERC, as the vertex regulator of the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (NESI), has the overriding power to promote the development and utilization of renewable energy in order to increase its contribution to Nigeria's electricity mix⁶⁸. The NERC is expected to increase the optimal development of the renewable electricity sector. By way of illustration, the Act stipulates that the Commission should simplify the licensing process for renewable electricity projects⁶⁹.

This is a historic development in that renewable energy projects were lopsided into the same licensing procedure as fossil fuel strategies. This invariably meant that fossil fuels had the same licensing procedure as renewable energy, except that fossil fuels had accumulated the benefit of experience of usage which translates to cheaper costs. For this reason, fossil fuels became a more palatable and better option in comparison to renewable energy. The licensing process was also complicated and expensive. The latter was argued to add to the already expensive initial capital costs of developing a renewable electricity project. As such, a simplified procedure which may likely be less expensive will reduce the additional costs of licensing which enhances the problem of affordability of the initial capital cost in the sector.

(NERC) was established as an independent regulatory body for the electricity industry in Nigeria.

⁶⁷ The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission is an independent body, established by the Electric Power Sector Reform Act of 2005 to undertake technical and economic regulation of the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry.

⁶⁸ The Act stimulates development and utilisation of renewable energy sources and the creation of an enabling environment to attract investments in renewable energy, in order to increase the contribution of renewable energy to the overall energy mix of Nigeria

⁶⁹ Ibid

The overall import is to make renewable energy more attractive to electricity investors than their fossil fuel counterparts. Another way that the NERC is expected to heighten the use of renewable energy is to ensure that the pricing mechanisms put in place by the licensees favour renewable energy consumers. As reiterated, the initial capital costs of most renewable electricity projects are significant and investors cannot easily afford them, especially with an underdeveloped capital market in Nigeria. To address this, the Act mandates NERC to provide incentives to support independent power producers who invest in the energy sector such that they are able to fund their activities while allowing for the generation of reasonable revenue to implement their operations⁷⁰.

8.5 Rural Electrification Fund (REF) and Rural Electrification Agency (REA)

In favour of the utilization of renewable energy, one of the Electricity Act's features also includes the creation of the Rural Electrification Fund (REF) which is managed by the Rural Electrification Agency ('REA' or 'the Agency')⁷⁰. According to the Electricity Act 2023, the REF was established and is solely committed to the promotion, provision and support of renewable electricity investments and projects in the rural and underserved areas of Nigeria⁷¹.

It is apt to mention that while the erstwhile Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA) 2005 also provided for the fund, it merely just stated that it was geared towards supporting rural electrification projects – both on-grid and off-grid. Thus, the REF under the EPSRA 2005 was supporting both renewable and fossil fuel electricity projects. Given that fossil fuel electricity strategies were already benefitting from accumulated decades of subsidies and experience to the exclusion of renewable energy strategies, uniform financial support as provided by the EPSRA 2005's REF will not specifically benefit renewable energy projects.

Furthermore, this new Electricity Act provides for the express abutment of the development of renewable energy and is therefore, unlike the ESPRA 2005, a clear-cut added advantage for the renewable energy industry. Relatedly, the Act mandates the REA to manage the operations of the REF⁷². In addition, the REA will also be promoting the advancement, accessibility and support of rural and underserved electrification including through the productive use and development of renewable energy.

The REA also introduces to the Act, the espousal of the facilitation of tax incentives and affordable interest loans for local producers of renewable energy products for electrification. The latter tax

⁷⁰ The agency exists to facilitate the provision of affordable power supply for residential, commercial, industrial and social activities in the rural and peri-urban areas of the country.

⁷¹ Sections 142 and 143 of the Electricity Act

⁷² Ibid

incentive will be handy in reducing the cost of investment in the renewable energy sector. Affordable loan interest will additionally ameliorate the considerable investment costs in the renewable energy sector especially when juxtaposed with fossil fuel investments. Moreover, the REA is saddled with the responsibility of executing renewable energy projects on their own, in rural areas. Notably, it has been assuming the same responsibility of developing rural electricity projects including renewable energy under the ESPRA 2005.

8.6 National Hydroelectric Power Producing Area Development Commission (the ‘N-HYPPADEC’ or the ‘Commission’)

The Act also created the National Hydroelectric Power Producing Area Development Commission (the ‘N-HYPPADEC’ or the ‘Commission’) – which is deemed to be a novel creation⁷³. The N-HYPPADEC is solely obligated to work with both the state and federal governments to promote the development of electricity from hydro energy⁷⁴. One may recall that, by way of the 2023 constitutional amendments, the state governments have now been empowered to generate, transmit and distribute electricity from on-grid and off-grid sources.

This is, therefore, in line with the N-HYPPADEC’s duty to work unrestrictedly with both state and federal governments to promote the utilization of hydroelectricity. The Commission is mandated to strictly promote, support and execute all plans pertaining to the development of hydroelectricity in Nigeria⁷⁵. Also, all ecological challenges arising from the overloading of dams and all other environmental hazards that may occur in the hydroelectric power-producing areas must be tackled by the N-HYPPADEC. The N-HYPPADEC’s establishment by the Act is, thus, indicative of the drafters of the Act and indeed, Nigeria’s firm dedication to providing energy security, increasing the use of renewable energy sources like hydro energy, and accomplishing its net-zero targets

8.7 Financial Obligations

Moreover, the Electricity Act caters for a feed-in tariff as provided for by law – i.e., the feed-in tariff is an obligation of the Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Company (NBETC) and all other independent licensees under the Act that will either be transmitting, generating or distributing electricity⁷⁶. The feed-in tariffs mandate the mentioned parties to treat as must-buy electricity produced from renewable energy for the purpose of being fed into the national grid. The rationale behind the feed-in tariffs is that the

⁷³ Section 82 of the Act

⁷⁴ Section 82 of the Act

⁷⁵ Ibid

⁷⁶ Ibid

national grid is not designed to accommodate intermittent sources of energy such as renewable.

Thus, costs of system upgrade and ancillary costs required for making the national grid fit for this purpose would ordinarily deter NBET and system operators from buying and transmitting renewable energy respectively⁷⁷. As such, the feed-in-tariffs innovation addresses the challenges of accommodating renewable electricity in the national grid by creating some mandatoriness on relevant parties while making sure renewable energy developers' foot the cost of system upgrade. This is in sync with what is obtainable from other jurisdictions, such as China, that have fared well in the development of the renewable energy sector.

The final feature of the Act as regards the advocacy for the use of renewable electricity is the 'renewable purchase obligation'⁷⁸. The 'renewable purchase obligation' imposes an obligation on bulk buyers/traders of electricity to ensure that they buy a certain percentage of their total purchase of electricity from renewable energy sources⁷⁹. To put it in plain words, if those who are licensed to trade and sell electricity to consumers seek to buy or sell electricity under the Act, the law stipulates that the NERC shall designate a certain percentage of electricity to them which must come from renewable energy sources⁸⁰.

By way of example, if the NBETC in buying electricity to trade or for new entrants, purchased 100% fossil fuel, the NERC will designate that 3% of the electricity purchased must be from the renewable energy mix. It is, therefore, crystal clear that the Act is the requisite tool that would galvanize the energy sector into actively transitioning from the dependability of fossil fuels to the efficient utilization of renewable energy sources in Nigeria.

8.8 Environmental Impact Assessment Act 1992

The Environmental Impact Assessment Act 1992 seeks to forestall the negative impacts of activities on the environment, including power generation and extraction. As at the time of its enactment, hydrocarbons constituted (and still constitute) a major source of energy for Nigeria, the generation and extraction of which had negative environmental impacts. The enactment of the Environmental Impact Assessment Act 1992 mandates project managers and parties to examine the likely impact of their activities on the environment before undertaking them. Under the current Guidelines 2017, a power-generating company or developer will be required to submit its environmental impact assessment to the

⁷⁷ Ibid

⁷⁸ Section 167 of the Act.

⁷⁹ Section 167, *ibid*

⁸⁰ Section 167, *ibid*

Federal Ministry of Environment and obtain permission or a licence to proceed with the project.

8.9 NEMSA Act 2015

The NEMSA Act 2015 seeks to enforce and maintain standards in power distribution. The NEMSA carries out technical inspections and testing for electrical materials. The standards are stipulated by the NERC in collaboration with the SON. In the judicial arena, there is minimal enforcement of the plethora of environmental laws in Nigeria as the case law seeking to promote renewable and clean generation of power has usually been focused on petroleum activities.

This is further crippled by technical principles such as cause of action, the doctrine of ripeness and *locus standi*. An ordinary citizen is therefore discouraged from approaching the court to enforce the environmental laws where he or she is not directly and personally affected more than other citizens. Although recent decisions by the Nigerian Supreme Courts seem to reverse this strict reasoning, there is still yet to be an express opening of the court's doors.

In cases such as *Centre For Oil Pollution Watch v. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation*,⁸¹ the court reiterated the need to switch from the carbon-polluting mindset. Also, in the case of *Amadi&Ors v. Essien*,⁸² the court affirmed the enforceability of electricity regulation in Nigeria. Finally, in the case of *Barr Mike Kpemi v. Benin Electricity Distribution Company PLC*⁸³, the court enforced the claimant's right to an electricity meter for the supply of electricity to his household.

8.10 Climate Change Act 2021

The Climate Change Act 2021 provides the framework for achieving low greenhouse gas emissions. Moreover, it ensures that climate change policies and actions are integrated with other related policies for promoting socioeconomic development and environmental integrity. It also ensures that private and public entities comply with stated climate change strategy targets and the National Climate Change Action Plan. The National Climate Action Plan is expected to be formulated every five years and is aimed at identifying activities to ensure that the national emission profile is consistent with carbon budget goals. In fulfilment of this expectation, Nigeria's National Action Plan was created to reduce short-lived climate pollutants (SLCPs).

The plan aims to improve air quality through adoption of 22 mitigation measures across eight sectors including transportation, residential, the oil & gas industry, agriculture and waste management. It is

⁸¹[2019] 5 NWLR (PT 1666) 518

⁸²[1993] LPELR-14644 (CA)

⁸³(2022) 4 CLRN 140

expected that the full implementation of the mitigating measures will be effective in reducing SLCPs, with an 83 per cent reduction in black carbon emissions by 2030 compared to a business-as-usual scenario, and a 61 per cent reduction in methane emissions. Nigeria, like many other countries, is committed to addressing climate change and reducing its carbon footprint. The transition to renewables offers a viable pathway to decrease reliance on fossil fuels, which are major contributors to greenhouse gas emissions.

9.0 CHALLENGES OF RENEWABLE ENERGY TRANSITION IN NIGERIA

a. Statutory Issue with Levy Administration

Several challenges limit investment in and development of renewable energy projects in Nigeria. Considering confusion in Sections 95(2) (c) and (e) regarding the levy to be administered by N-HYPPDEC for host community development for communities where hydroelectricity is generated in Nigeria. On one hand, Section 95(2) (c) imposes a 5% levy of all revenue accruing from power generated by various GenCos in the affected communities, while Section 95(2) (e) on the other hand, exempts hydroelectric GenCos from the application of the levy.

The above appears to be a contradiction given that the Section relates to hydroelectric power producing areas in Nigeria. This error is so critical to the growth or otherwise of competitiveness of renewable components given how coordination of the levy continues to affect companies. Several other challenges limit investment in and development of renewable energy projects in Nigeria. These challenges include:

b. Critical Issue around Mini-Grid Scope

Interestingly, the Act confers exclusive powers on states with respect to mini-grids⁸⁴. The Act provides that it shall be the responsibility of State Electricity Boards or any State authority by whatever appellation, to grant licences for mini-grids by Independent Electricity Distribution Network Operators (IEDN/IETNO) or Independent Electricity Transmission Network/Independent Electricity Transmission Network Operators (IETN/IETNOs), and provide the framework for the operation of such licensees, including frameworks for investment in electricity utilities within the state.

On the flip side, the powers of the federation (exercised through NERC) over mini-grids as provided in the Act,⁸⁵ is restricted to situations where (a) a federating state(s) has no legal and institutional framework in place for the regulation of mini-grids, IEDNs, IETNs or related electricity services; or (b)

⁸⁴ Section 63(7) of the Act.

⁸⁵Section 63(7) of the Act.

the operation of such IEDN/IEDNOs, IETN/IETNOs or electricity generation, transmission and distribution undertaking within any state of the federation relies on any part of the national grid for its operations.

Three issues are immediately discernible from the foregoing laudable provisions of the Act. First, the Act does not define mini-grids, second, there is a clear risk of overlap and duplication of licences, and third, it is not entirely clear what is meant by reliance on any part of the national grid. The Act does not define mini-grids, thus creating room for NERC to define the concept by regulation, which may in itself give rise to a restrictive meaning.

Indeed, by para. 3 of the Mini-Grid Regulations, 2016 issued by NERC, mini-grid refers to an isolated or integrated local generation and distribution system with installed capacity between 0kW and 1MW, capable of serving numerous end-users. It is clear from the foregoing that NERC's definition of mini-grid is by reference to installed capacity, rather than by reference to the structure or sophistication of the system (off grid, IEDN/IEDNOs/IETN/IETNOs). NERC's definition is rather different from the much wider definition of "mini grid renewable power system" in the Act, which is defined as "a network of electricity supply from renewable energy technologies which is not connected to the grid".

The Act did not define or restrict what constitutes "mini grid renewable power system" by reference to installed capacity, thus making a plausible case for the same approach to be adopted to the definition of "mini-grid". The risk of overlap and duplication of licences can arise where an electric power company only operates within a state but is nevertheless in one way or another "relying on a part of the national grid" in its operations. For example, possibly, in the sense that power that flows into the mini-grid also flows through the national grid before or after flowing into the mini-grid. The Constitution did not qualify the legislative powers of the states in the manner sought to be done under the Act. Indeed, the only requirement to trigger the regulatory oversight of states is that the electric power company must be operating solely within the borders of the relevant state. A critical question that arises is whether a mini-grid power system can still be said to be operating within state borders (in the sense that all its customers or target area is within the boundaries of a state) when it is connected to or relies on any part of the national grid.

By the Act, national grid refers to "any electrical power system that transcends the boundaries of one or more states in Nigeria or that is connected to a country outside Nigeria for the purpose of electricity generation, transmission, system operation, distribution, supply and trading".

Consequently, a mini-grid operator or any other licensee that is connected to any part of the national grid

(generation, transmission, distribution, supply or trading) can be said to be operating across state borders, even if its ultimate end-users are resident within the boundaries of one state. Thus, a licensee seeking to be exclusively licensed by a state must not be connected to any part of the entire gamut of generation, transmission, system operation, distribution, supply, and trading infrastructures that constitute the national grid.

Nevertheless, a tricky question that will arise is whether a state licensee (e.g., a Genco) that is not directly connected to the national grid, will be deemed to be relying on a part of the national grid where another state licensee (e.g. a Disco) connected to it, is also connected to the national grid (e.g., by buying additional electric power from the national electricity pool). We think in such situations, the scope of the licensee's activities as stated in its licence will determine the appropriate regulator. A Disco or Genco that is acting within its licence should not be deemed to be acting across state borders if a different licensee it is doing business with is connected to the national grid. The Act says "rely on" not "related to" or "indirectly connected to".

b. Ambiguity in Contextualising “Greenfield Sites Within

The Act further provides that the franchise area of IETNLs licensed under state laws shall be restricted to “greenfield sites within the States”, while the franchise of the transmission service provider licensed by the Commission will extend over areas where the transmission service provider has its transmission facilities.⁸⁶ It is not clear what is meant by “greenfield sites within the States”.

Similarly, the restriction on state licensees from having transmission rights over “areas that the transmission service provider has its transmission facilities” is also ambiguous. Two meanings may be canvassed. First, it is unclear whether “greenfield sites” refers simply to an entirely new right of way different from sites or land areas where transmission facilities traverses; or second, whether greenfield sites refer to “areas” that are not connected to, or catered for by, a transmission facility. Indeed, a third meaning may even be canvassed: a “greenfield” may refer to a defined area of land (measurable in square meter) over which capital sums (as may be stipulated in a regulation) has been ‘auditably’ spent size plus costs approach.

Similarly, “areas that the transmission service provider has its transmission facilities” may also mean two things: first the land area on which the transmission facilities subject to wind are constructed; or second, the areas over which a transmission facility cover, that is, a service coverage approach. It is

⁸⁶ Section 66(3) of the Act.

clear that while the first meaning may be justifiable from a technical perspective, the second is on a collision course with the Constitution.

Except the foregoing qualifications are given a narrow construction and the first meanings adopted, it would appear that the two qualifications have introduced, through the backdoor, the same restriction that the constitutional amendment sought to remove. By attempting to restrict the transmission coverage of state licensees operating within state borders to “greenfield sites” over which the transmission service provider has no facilities, the National Assembly will have unconstitutionally qualified and restricted the lawmaking powers of the state in electricity transmission matters, contrary to the provisions of the Constitution, as amended.

The rights of states to make laws over electricity matters (including generation, transmission and distribution) are not circumscribed by the existence or otherwise of any component of the national grid in or around the state. The coverage area of state transmission licensees cannot therefore be circumscribed by a federal law, when states literally have constitutional powers to make laws and grant licences over areas covered by the national grid provided the operations of the licensee is strictly within the borders of the relevant state.

c. Electricity Distribution and Electricity Supply Quagmire

The Act recognizes electricity supply as an activity distinct from distribution. Thus, it empowers the Commission to direct the disaggregation of distribution licences into supply and distribution licensed companies.⁸⁷ The Commission is to execute a transfer scheme for disaggregating existing distribution companies or licensees into supply and distribution licences. It is not entirely clear how the disaggregation will be implemented. It is very likely that electricity suppliers will function much the same way the Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading PLC (NBET) functions today, but with greater involvement in the energy market. It is not entirely clear if the electricity suppliers will directly be in charge of issuing and handling the settlement of consumer bills, while Discos remain in charge of the distribution networks and infrastructures. Whichever way, it is likely that electricity suppliers will act as some form of credit cushion in the NESI.

It also remains to be seen if the Discos will be happy to give up the supply component of their business, particularly considering that asset valuation and acquisition during the electricity sector privatization programme, was on the basis of a composite distribution and supply portfolio. If anything, cases such as

⁸⁷ Section 68(6) of the Act

the dispute between Enugu Electricity Distribution Company, the Geometric Power Aba Limited and the Bureau of Public Enterprises over the Aba Ringed-Fenced Area,⁸⁸ show that Discos value their investment and acquisition as a composite investment, and may therefore resist the disaggregation without adequate compensation.

The success of any such resistance cannot, however, be guaranteed as the Discos will essentially be left with the same assets and the same rights to distribute electricity over the same designated area—therefore there will be no expropriation in principle. The only difference is that the Discos will no longer be able to directly collect or enforce payment from customers.

d. Statutory Issue with Metering

The new Electricity Act also failed to give a mandatory legislative iron curtain for metering, and instead gives the Commission the discretion to set, and extend, the deadline for metering as the NERC deems fit.

10 RECOMMENDATIONS

To spur investment in energy infrastructure the following suggestions are imminent thus:

- a. The Electricity Act should have clearly established a roadmap towards market-determined electricity tariff with minimal regulator intervention in deserving cases. It is clear that the electricity sector is labouring under a deteriorating liquidity problem and hence investment in the electricity sector has been on downward spiral. To promote accelerated private sector investment, deliberate efforts ought to have been made to include and consolidate existing incentives in the electricity sector (including incentives under the pioneer status regime) in the Act. This would have made for more efficient marketing of the investment opportunities in Nigeria’s electric power sector;
- b. There should be a broader and clear definition of mini-grids in accordance with the philosophy of the Act;
- c. The concept of “greenfields” and “areas covered by the national grid” has to be carefully delineated to avoid potential constitutional issues, among others.
- d. There is a need for further amendment of the Act to give a comprehensive legislative details on metering to remove the current NERC’s discretion which could be subjected to political

⁸⁸Business Day Nigeria, BPE Compels Enugu Disco to Handover Aba Ring Fence to Aba Power Limited, September 10, 2015, accessed on 23 November, 2023.

manipulation fraud.

11.0 CONCLUSION

The enactment of the Act is a welcome development in the Nigerian electric power sector. It gives impetus to the renewed hope agenda of the current administration of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in order to develop and expand Nigeria's electricity market. The Act recognizes the concurrent powers of the states in this regard.